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Enhancement of Noise Mitigation of Natural Fibre Composites with Perforation

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Agenda

- Introduction
- Fabrication
- Experimental Method
- Results
- Conclusion

Introduction

Introduction

- Emphasis on green technology has been growing over the past decades.
- Many ways to go green.
- Natural fibres are advantageous over synthetic fibres (most importantly, environmentally-friendly).
- Natural fibres have been used in automobiles for noise mitigation.
- Use of natural fibres could be extended to other applications owing to their good acoustical properties.

Introduction

- Micro-perforated plates (MPPs) are new-generation sound absorbers and they are commonly used as noise absorption panels.
- They are plates with very small perforations (holes) whose diameter is in the order of a millimeter.
- In this paper, we present the preliminary study of incorporating micro-perforations and holes in natural fibre composites with the intention of improving the low frequency absorption properties of these natural fibre composite plates.

Fabrication

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Fabrication of natural composite panel

- ❖ 12-ply flax fibre composite (7 layers of (PP) and 6 layers of (FF))

- ❖ Preheated (80°C for 1 h) and laid alternately in 0 and 90 degrees orientation

Circular shape obtained by Water-jet cutting machine

Microscopic image of drilled hole

Experimental Method

Sound transmission loss (STL) measurement

Impedance tube setup
(BSWA Inc.)

Sample mounting process

- ❖ The sound transmission loss of each sample was measured in four different orientations.
- ❖ An average STL values of three replications was taken into the final consideration.
- ❖ Influence of various factors on the STL performance were measured.
- ❖ For the measurement of humidity effect, samples were placed in controlled environment and experiments were performed at every 48 hours.

Results

Influence of environmental factors (Temp. and Humidity)

- ❖ Natural fibers are prone to absorb moisture in humid environment.
- ❖ It affects the acoustic characteristics of the fabricated composite panel.
- ❖ Speed of sound through the composite increases with increase in relative humidity.
- ❖ Humidity effects are significant only at higher frequencies above 2 kHz.

Speed of sound:

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma P}{\rho}} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma RT}{M}}$$

P = ambient pressure

ρ = gas density

γ = specific heat ratio

R = Univ. gas constant

T = absolute temp.

M = Mean Mol. Weight

Influence of perforated hole size

- ❖ Below the 600 Hz:

$$STL_{d=0.5 \text{ \& } 1 \text{ mm}} > STL_{\text{solid plate}}$$

- ❖ Frequency range ($600 \text{ Hz} \leq f \leq 1050 \text{ Hz}$):

$$STL_{\text{solid plate}} >$$

- ❖ Acoustic Impedance of the perforated plate:

$$Z = Z_R + jZ_i$$

Z_R : Real part, represents viscous effect, and
 Z_i : Imaginary part, represents the inertia of the air inside the hole.

- ❖ **Case I: Micro-perforated hole ($d < 1 \text{ mm}$):**

- Resistive part dominates
- Motion of the fluid inside the hole is controlled by the friction between the air and the inner surface of the hole.

- ❖ **Case I: Micro-perforated hole ($d > 1 \text{ mm}$)**

- Real part reduces rapidly with a increase in diameter.
- Inertia effect dominates over the resistive part.

Influence of number of perforated holes

- ❖ **For the frequency range (100 to 550 Hz):**
 - Optimum no. of holes (N) for higher STL = 11 to 13.
 - Improvement in STL = 25 % (Approx.).
- ❖ **For the frequency range (650 to 1150 Hz):**
 - Optimum no. of holes (N) for higher STL = 0 to 1.
- ❖ **The overall STL is lower in case of N = 15 and 17.**

Conclusion

Conclusion

- ❖ The most optimum method to drill natural composites would be to use high spindle speed with low feed rate.
- ❖ Humidity effects are significant only at higher frequencies above 2 kHz.
- ❖ For the frequency range of 100 to 550 Hz, the optimum number of holes for higher Sound transmission loss is between 11 to 13. There is an approximately improvement of 25% for sound transmission loss.

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Thank You

We make a lot of noise but we are sound people

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